

TABLE I

Complex	Thermal stability temp. °C	Decomposition temp. °C	Approx. residue formation temp. °C	Residue %	
				Theoretical	Observed
Ni(II)-HDCMBAOX	180	240	800	10.66	10.75
Cu(II)-HDCMBAOX	180	200	760	11.17	11.22
Pd(II)-HDCMBAOX	140	200	780	14.24	14.29

copper salicyldoxime⁵ which is stable upto 140°. It may be pointed out that the final weights of the residues were almost equal to weights of residues calculated from the molecular formulae of the complexes (Table I).

None of the Ni(II), Cu(II) and Pd(II) complexes with HDCMBAOX showed any change in colour with blue litmus or neutral FeCl₃. These show that there is no free phenolic group in the complex molecule.

Vosburgh and Copper's method⁶ showed that Ni(II) formed only one complex with HDCMBAOX having λ_{max} at 370 nm in the pH range 9.0-9.5. Subsequent studies were, therefore, undertaken at pH 9.2. Beer's law was valid upto 1010.5 ppm of Ni(II). There was no change in the absorbance within the experimental pH 9.0-9.5 of the system. There was again no change in colour even on keeping it for 25 hr and there was no change in the absorbance at room temperature either. The composition of the complex was found to be 1:2 (metal: ligand) by the application of Job's method⁷ of continuous variation and mole ratio method⁸. Ringbom method⁹ was applied for the determination of optimum concentration range for effective concentration determination of Ni(II) and it was found to be 33.69 to 78.62 ppm. The stability constant of the complex was calculated by the mole ratio method and was found to be 5.9833×10^6 . The standard free energy of formation was 9.707 kcal mol⁻¹ and entropy was 31.01 e.u. All these parameters were calculated at 40°.

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Influence of Concentration and Nature of Different Supporting Electrolytes on the Kinetics of Electrode Reaction of Bromophenol Blue

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WE have reported¹ the mechanism of polarographic reduction of bromophenol blue over the pH range 1.81-11.98 (BR buffer). The present paper describes the influence of concentration and nature of a number of supporting electrolytes, viz., NaNO₃, NaCl, NaClO₄, KNO₃, KCl, K₂SO₄, KCNS, Ba(NO₃)₂, Sr(NO₃)₂, Ca(NO₃)₂ and Mg(NO₃)₂, on the kinetics of the electrode reaction of bromophenol blue.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade and their stock solutions were prepared in conductivity water. Other experimental details are the same as mentioned earlier¹. The number of electrons (n) involved in the reduction process of bromophenol blue at d.m.e. was determined by millicoulometric method of DeVries and Kroon². This gave the value of n equal to 2 at pH 3.29 in the presence of different supporting electrolytes. Knowing the value of n, Ilkovic equation was used to calculate the value of the diffusion-coefficient, D, of bromophenol blue at different concentrations of supporting electrolytes. The potential-dependent rate constant, $k_{f,h}$, was calculated by Koutecky's^{3,4} method. The kinetic parameters, αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$ were calculated⁵ from the plots of $\log k_{f,h}$ vs $E_{d.e.}$. Throughout the measurements, the current at the end of the drop (i.e. the maximum current) was recorded for the reasons given by Meites^{6a}.

Results and Discussion

Bromophenol blue gives well-defined reduction wave at pH 3.29 (BR buffer) in the presence of different supporting electrolytes of varying concentrations (0.05-1.0 M). The wave-height in each case is diffusion-controlled as evidenced by the linearity of i_d vs $h^{1/2}$ plots and their passing through the origin. Various criteria^{6b,7,8} of ascertaining the irreversibility of the electrode reaction of bromophenol blue indicate that the reduction process is

NOTES

TABLE 1—VALUES OF POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR THE ELECTRODE REACTION OF BROMOPHENOL BLUE AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF SUPPORTING ELECTROLYTES IN BR BUFFER OF pH 3.29

[Bromophenol blue] = $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$; Temp. $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$; $m = 1.13 \text{ mg/sec}$; $t = 3.6 \text{ sec}$; $m^{2/3} t^{1/3} = 1.35 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/3}$ (0.1 M KCl, open circuit); $h_{\text{eff}} = 37.5 \text{ cm}$.

Conc. of supporting electrolytes	i_d (μA)	$-E_{1/2}$ (V) (SCE)	Slope (mV)	$D \times 10^6$ (cm^2/sec)	αn_a	$k_{f,h}^0 \times 10^5$ (cm/sec)	$k_{f,h} \times 10^4$ (cm/sec)
				NaNO ₃			
0.05	4.95	0.390	85	6.74	0.66	2.53	8.36
0.10	4.88	0.396	90	6.56	0.62	3.26	6.44
0.50	4.82	0.397	118	6.38	0.58	3.78	6.36
1.00	4.82	0.398	119	6.39	0.54	4.44	5.90
				NaCl			
0.05	4.55	0.384	75	5.70	0.74	1.09	10.38
0.10	4.55	0.392	80	5.70	0.72	1.76	8.70
0.50	4.29	0.398	111	5.60	0.71	1.77	7.25
				NaClO ₄			
0.05	4.55	0.378	64	5.70	0.83	0.52	16.66
0.10	4.55	0.380	65	5.70	0.80	0.81	7.24
0.50	4.29	0.398	75	5.06	0.74	1.14	6.44
1.00	4.22	0.400	105	4.91	0.71	1.15	5.07
				KNO ₃			
0.05	4.55	0.392	72	5.71	0.89	0.68	7.85
0.10	4.36	0.394	95	5.22	0.86	0.67	7.26
0.50	4.22	0.408	100	4.91	0.86	0.03	3.86
1.00	4.16	0.410	112	4.76	0.85	0.47	3.63
				KCl			
0.05	4.22	0.416	63	4.91	0.86	0.49	2.68
0.10	4.16	0.420	76	4.76	0.86	0.35	2.44
1.00	3.43	0.420	100	3.23	0.74	0.17	2.17
				KCNS			
0.05	4.49	0.406	74	5.54	0.74	0.78	2.60
0.10	4.36	0.416	74	5.22	0.74	0.73	2.40
0.50	4.29	0.420	76	5.00	0.74	0.49	2.29
1.00	4.22	0.422	84	4.71	0.70	0.28	1.98
				K ₂ SO ₄			
0.05	4.82	0.416	70	6.38	0.77	0.34	2.25
0.10	4.62	0.430	84	5.87	0.68	1.00	2.20
0.50	4.49	0.440	98	5.54	0.53	2.34	1.95
				Sr(NO ₃) ₂			
0.05	4.55	0.396	76	5.07	0.68	1.53	5.58
0.10	4.22	0.408	80	4.91	0.59	1.18	3.21
0.50	4.02	0.418	84	4.46	0.59	1.02	3.00
				Ba(NO ₃) ₂			
0.05	4.09	0.438	71	4.61	0.89	0.13	1.43
0.10	4.42	0.428	67	5.38	1.10	0.04	2.02
				Ca(NO ₃) ₂			
0.05	4.29	0.408	76	5.06	0.92	1.07	2.44
0.10	4.22	0.415	88	4.91	0.88	0.90	2.67
0.50	3.96	0.390	100	4.31	0.97	0.23	4.37
				Mg(NO ₃) ₂			
0.05	4.88	0.380	110	6.56	0.86	0.18	12.61
0.10	4.62	0.374	105	5.80	1.00	8.50	12.95

irreversible in the presence of increasing concentrations of different supporting electrolytes. Table 1 records the values of polarographic characteristics and of kinetic parameters at varying concentrations of different supporting electrolytes. It was shown in an earlier publication¹ that the depolarizer follows the same course of reduction mechanism in the pH range 1.81-6.80 where two electrons and a proton are involved in the rate-determining step i.e., $n_a = 2$ and $H^+ = 1$. It is in this background that the present study has been done at pH 3.29 (BR buffer).

It is clear from Table 1 that the value of the product αn_a decreases with increasing concentrations

of NaNO₃, NaCl, NaClO₄, KNO₃, KCl, KCNS, K₂SO₄ and Sr(NO₃)₂ while it increases in the case of Ba(NO₃)₂, Ca(NO₃)₂ and Mg(NO₃)₂. Since the decrease or increase in the value of αn_a is indiscrete and at no stage the two consecutive values vary by a factor of 2, the possibility of a decrease or an increase in the value of αn_a due to a change in n_a may be ruled out. It may, thus, be safely concluded that it is α which is decreasing in the case of NaNO₃, NaCl, NaClO₄, KNO₃, KCl, KCNS, K₂SO₄ and Sr(NO₃)₂ while it is increasing in the case of Ba(NO₃)₂, Ca(NO₃)₂ and Mg(NO₃)₂. This implies^{9,10} that the irreversible electrode reaction of bromophenol blue is rendered increa-

singly more irreversible with increasing concentrations of NaNO_3 , NaCl , NaClO_4 , KNO_3 , KCl , KCNS , K_2SO_4 and $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ while it tends to be less irreversible in the case of increasing concentrations of $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$.

A perusal of Table 1 shows that there is no regularity in the variation of $k_{f,h}^0$ values with increasing concentrations of the supporting electrolytes. Meites⁶ has hinted at the limitation of $k_{f,h}^0$ in interpreting the results. However, the influence of the concentration of the supporting electrolytes on the rate of the electrode reaction of bromophenol blue can be studied^{9,11,12} in terms of the value of the potential-dependent rate constant ($k_{f,h}$) at a suitable potential which should be such as to lie between the potentials corresponding to the foot and the plateau of the polarographic wave, because⁸ at such a potential both the rate of electron transfer and diffusion determine the magnitude of the current. In the present system this potential has been taken as -0.38 V (SCE) and the values of $k_{f,h}$ at this potential have been listed in Table 1. A perusal of the values shows that $k_{f,h}$ decreases with increasing concentrations of NaNO_3 , NaCl , NaClO_4 , KNO_3 , KCl , K_2SO_4 , KCNS and $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, while reverse is the case with $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$. It follows from this that whereas in the former cases the electrode reaction tends to become more irreversible, it becomes less irreversible in the latter.

The influence of the nature of the cations and anions constituting the supporting electrolytes on the kinetics of the electrode reaction of bromophenol blue has been studied by comparing the values of $k_{f,h}$ (at -0.38 V versus SCE) at a certain concentration (0.1M) of the supporting electrolytes. The order of $k_{f,h}$ values is for cations (as nitrates): $\text{Mg}^{2+} > \text{K}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{Sr}^{2+} > \text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{Ba}^{2+}$; for anions (as potassium salts): $\text{NO}_3^- > \text{CNS}^- > \text{Cl}^- > \text{SO}_4^{2-}$.

The role of cations and anions of the supporting electrolytes in changing the value of $k_{f,h}$ is related with their specific adsorption on the surface of the electrode.

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Determination of Stability Constants of 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-sulphasomidine Complexes with La^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Dy^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , Gd^{3+} and Y^{3+}

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THE present communication reports the potentiometric studies on 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-sulphasomidine and its complexes with some trivalent metal ions. The dissociation constants (pK_1 and pK_2) of the reagent and the formation constants ($\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$) of its metal chelates have been determined potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹.

Experimental

The ligand 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-sulphasomidine was prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and the amine in alcohol-DMF mixture for ~ 2 hr. The crude product was repeatedly crystallised to get an analytically pure compound, m.p. 220°.

All the metal perchlorates used were prepared from metal salts and A.R. grade perchloric acid. These were standardised complexometrically by EDTA titrations².

Other experimental details were the same as reported earlier³.

Results and Discussion

It may be mentioned that the ligand does not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental conditions described. This was indicated by rapid attainment of equilibrium during the course of titration and by the absence of any significant drift in pH even after 2 hr. This was further confirmed by the of a sample titration mixture from time to time.

In the ligand, it is the phenolic (OH) group which takes part in complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by the metal ion during chelation. As only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated, Y, the number of dissociable protons attached to each ligand molecule is one.

From the titration curves, \bar{n}_A values at various B values (pH meter readings) were calculated and the formation curve (B vs \bar{n}_A) was plotted. The pK_1^H and pK_2^H corresponding to phenolic H and imino NH were obtained by half integral method at $\bar{n}_A=0.5$ and 1.5, respectively. These were further corroborated by plotting the graph of $\log(\bar{n}_A/1-\bar{n}_A)$ vs B and $\log(2-\bar{n}_A/\bar{n}_A-1)$ vs B, respectively.

From the titration curves, \bar{n} and pL values for metal-ligand systems were also calculated. From the curves (\bar{n} vs pL), $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values were